

Working Conditions of Women in Agriculture

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Sultana, I., and

N. Mubeen Sultana.

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I.Sultana

Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of Economics, The New College, Chennai

N.Mubeen Sultana

Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Sociology, Queen Mary’s College, Chennai

Abstract

Women are the backbone of the rural economy. Based on the data of 2012, India is the fourth largest agricultural sector in the world. In rural India, 84% of the women depend on agriculture. Apart from household work and family responsibility, rural women play a major role in the agricultural sector. Various study shows that the participation of women in agriculture have a greater impact on the productivity as well as food security. It also helps to guarantee their self –sustenance. Statistical Data of 2017 shows that the working women folk in agriculture has been increased from 18 to 21 percent since 2006. In June 2016, female casual workers were less than average of the last decade. Rural women ensure food security for their communities, build climate resilience and strengthen economies”.(Rural Women and girls-february 2018/UN Women).According to ILOSTAT database 2018, Percentage of female employment in agriculture in 1991 was 76% and in 2017 it was drastically reduced to 56%. This paper throws light on the status and economic conditions of women workers in the rural economy. It also highlights the role played by the women folk to increase agricultural production. This paper is based on the secondary data taken from various journals, articles and from online sources.

Keywords: Women, Agriculture, production, employment

Introduction

Agriculture in India defines female tradition, social relations and gender roles. Study shows that 84% of women folk in India are engaged in agriculture for their livelihood. According to the famous scientist Swaminathan, It was a woman who first initiated the art and science of farming. The increasing role of women in agriculture tends to increase the GDP level in the country. Female labour participation in rural areas is more than in urban areas. By supporting rural women, we can break the vicious circle so that poverty can be reduced and the agricultural production can be expanded.

Methodology

This study is based on the secondary data which was collected from various journals, books, government reports, websites and NSSO data etc.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the role of women in agriculture in India
- To examine the employment and wages of women workers in agriculture.

Role of Women in Agriculture

Various Study shows that 78% of Women are engaged in agriculture compared to men of 63% and 70% of work was done by the women workers. It shows that the more number of workers are engaged in agriculture are women. According to UN Report, half of the agricultural production are done by the women. Women are the primary users of natural resources like land , water and forest etc. They have close relationship with those than any other natural resources .So rural women are considered responsible for the agricultural production in the country. More than the production they considered the goddess of the land.

Women workers in India

“A recent study conducted by Women and Population Division of FAO shows that in the developing countries women provide 70 % of agricultural labour, 60 to 80% labour for food production,100% for processing food stuffs, 80% for food storage and transport, 90% for water and fuel”(1) Women those who are engaged in the agricultural work are mostly illiterate. They are engaged in sowing seeds, harvesting, transplanting etc along with their domestic household activities. They are paid very less compared to men, though they do more work than menfolk. Gender Wage disparity present in all the activities. They do not have the power of decision-making in the household as well as in the farmwork.

Table: 1 Rural Female Work Participation in India 1961-2001

Census Year	Female
1961	31.4
1971	15.5
1981	23.2
1991	26.7
2001	23.1

Source: Government of India, Census Reports

Table 1 shows the rural female participation in India from 1961-2001. It clearly shows the female work participation in 1961 was 31.4 and it was gradually reduced to 23.1 in 2001. This is because of various problems which they face during the span of their work which are explained below.

Women Workers in Tamil Nadu

According to Geetha Narayanan, a member of the Tamil Nadu Federation of Women Farmers’ Rights (TNFWFR), Women are often not considered as farmers because the legal recognition is derived from land ownership despite of playing the major role in food production. “On an average, a woman spends 3,300 hours in the field in a crop season against 1,860 hours by a man. But only 12.69% of rural woman have operational land ownership and women farmers commit suicides, too”. (2)

According to the National Crime Records Bureau, 472 of the 5,650 farmers who committed suicide in 2014 were women. “But the administration neither counts this as farmer suicide nor compensates her family because she does not own the land.”

Socio-Economic conditions of women workers in agriculture

The Socio-Economic conditions of women workers in our country is very poor. It is measured by calculating the income of the Women agricultural labour and the number of days which they are employed. It is also depend upon the consumption level and the indebtedness of the women workers. Apart from the field work, they are also have to take care of their families and they are highly responsible for caring and nurturing. “Among female marginal workers 47.91 per cent are cultivators 41.43 per cent are agricultural labourers and 1.64 per cent are engaged in livestock, fisheries and forestry remaining 17.62 per cent female main workers and 9.02 per cent female marginal workers are in non-agricultural setor”.(3)

Table:2 Distributions of Female Workers in India 1961-2001

Year	Total female	Cultivators	Agricultural Labourers
1961	212467	33103 (55.7)	14171 (23.9)
1971	263900	9266 (29.6)	15794 (50.5)
1981	321357	14932 (33.2)	20768 (46.2)
1991	402813	22871 (34.5)	28833 (43.6)
2001	495738	41299 (41.51)	50093 (50.35)

Source: Government of India, Census Reports

Table 2 shows the distribution of female workers in India in 1961-2001. It explains the participation of female workers as cultivators and agricultural labourers.

Women have major constraints for participation in agriculture is as follows:

- 1) Unequal Land Rights
 - 2) Limited Access to Use of Resources
 - 3) Lack of Equipment and Appropriate Technology
 - 4) Limited Contact with Agricultural Extension
 - 5) Lack of Access to Credit
 - 6) Lower Level of Education
- (Raveendaran, 2006)

Specific Technologies for women workers in Agriculture

- Under the project” Identification and evaluation of interactive learning modules for dissemination of homestead technologies” Improved method of paddy parboiling procedures are done. During paddy parboiling, by the latest technology (paddy par boiling unit) the heart beat rate and energy expenditure were significantly reduced and the out put also increased from 35 kg per batch to 75kg per batch. The time duration of this process is also reduced from 2 days to 6 hours. Considering the latest method of paddy par boiling, an interactive learning module is being developed which will be useful for trainers in disseminating the technology.
- Several developments were made Under the project on “Reducing drudgery of women in agricultural operations “Design refinement in sitting type groundnut decorticator for women workers for better ergonomic performance—“These refinements included increase in handle length from 32 to 37cm, increase in sitting stool height from 20 to 30 cm and change in wooden base design for easy packing and transport. The women workers are very comfortable in using this equipment as the work could be done in sitting posture”(4)

Gender Mainstreaming

Since participation of women folk is high in the rural community, they are more exposed to manmade and natural calamities. They are the one who affect during poverty than menfolk. Gender mainstreaming is nothing but the priorities are given to both men and women equally. Government has taken several steps to accelerate the realization of gender equity. To facilitate and monitor for its full realization, the ministry of agriculture implements the new structural organization of gender mainstreaming where the women, children and youth are given priorities.

De-feminisation and male migration in agriculture

Male migration has become dominant in the field of agriculture. Most of the young men about the age of 12 to 14 years are the migrants and they are migrating to kerala or Assam. They often discontinued their studies and involved themselves in working as labour to support their families. According to the study of Merel van Andel (2016) shows 34% of the young boys discontinued their studies before completing std 10 to support their family with the additional income. It is said that because of male migration, hiring of agriculture labourers has become difficult and it leads to the situation that the landowners hire labours from other villages and the women are not allotted for these jobs as it has been considered that these jobs are only suitable for men.(5)

Reducing GHG Emissions

Changes in the energy used by women in agriculture can bring number of changes in the production process especially in the field of crop production and social reproduction. The Green house gas emission can be reduced by shifting the household cooking from carbon – biomass fuels to LPG. Shifting can also done from extracting groundwater to utilise surface water. Reduction of GHG can takes place by shifting from inorganic fertilizer to adopt latest technology which reduces the emission by providing more crop per unit of input or less seed per kilogram of output.(6)

MGNREGA Programme

This Paper also highlights the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) which provides 100 days of wage employment to the rural households in every financial year. It results in the highest female labour participation in the rural areas though it provides employment to both men folk and women folk for the equal wage. MGNREGA ensures that at least 33 per cent of the participating labourers are women. Provisions are also available to the women workers such as childcare facilities and the place where they work would be within 5 kilometres from their residence. These facilities are provided to remove the difficulties of women and to improve the active participation.

Problems faced by women workers in agriculture

As rural women plays a dual role i.e household work and field work, they face enormous number of problems . The main problems which they face are long working duration, lack of skill, low wages, poor health, physical and mental weakness, lack of training, lack of financial assistance etc. They lack in the participation of panchayat, MSP etc. They are not encouraged to become the owner of the land assets. The role in decision making is completely negligible. “In Salbari only 28 days of employment were available in 2015 and that was not enough to uplift the socio-economic condition of a household substantially”(7). Study shows that in many countries the work done by the women towards agriculture is considered as only a help rather the contribution done towards promoting agricultural production.

Suggestions

- Government should expand the projects beyond crop production and adopt new techniques to increase the income and employment opportunities for women.
- New programmes and projects must be created in order to mobilize the resources, improve micro enterprises to provide credit at reasonable rate and raw materials to the women workers.
- Ministry of Agriculture can join hands with other organizations to improve and develop New Programmes for the welfare of women workers and to improve agricultural production.
- Capacity building programmes must be provided and training should be given on gender issues.
- Change should be made and make up the mind of the society towards women and girls and prevailing mal practices must be reduced.

Conclusion

Agricultural women workers are illiterate and ignorant. Though they involve themselves actively in the production process, their participation are neglected. They lack equal access to credit, agricultural inputs and infrastructure etc. women are responsible for most of the household activities as well as rearing of livestock, working in the field etc. This additional work burden is unpaid and limits women's capacity. However, working women have been under the process of development in these days and this is true in the case of our country.

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